

- The ELIXIR **Marine Metagenomics Community** was established in 2015 as part of the ELIXIR EXCELERATE project
- Major focus of the **Marine Metagenomics Community** included:
 - Established metagenomics analysis pipelines (Mgnify, MetaPIPE, BioMaS and MetaShot)
 - Definition of reference databases (ITSOOneDB, MAR Sequence Databases, MetaCOXI)
 - Adoption of formal pipeline description tools (CWL, Nextflow)
- The emerging **Microbiome Community** was established by ELIXIR HoN meeting on September 14th, 2023
- A **Microbiome Community** White Paper was submitted to F1000 and is currently under review
- Scope of the community:
 - providing the necessary **infrastructures** required to perform **reproducible** analysis of nucleotide sequence data derived from a microbiome
 - support best practices in **data stewardship**
 - foster interactions amongst **communities** wishing to undertake microbiome research (clinicians, ecologists, agritech, biotechnology, nutritionists, etc)

Leadership

Bérénice Batut
Elixir -DE

Rob Finn
EMBL - EBI

Eric Pelletier
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Elixir -HUB

The context within Elixir

Objectives of the Microbiome Community

Area	Objective
Near-term (2 years timeframe)	
Community Expansion	Survey of needs, key datasets, data analysis approaches, 'omics data types and biome specific specialisation
	Identify key experts involved in viral, prokaryotic and eukaryotic analysis
	Establish and share a strategic technical roadmap with the Communities and Platforms, highlighting key contacts
	Identify relevant funding calls, with the aid of building microbiome research informatics capacities and connecting to key experts in other 'omics (e.g. metaproteomics)
Training	Increase awareness of microbiome tools, resources, and their applicability to different microbiomes
	Address knowledge gaps in generating and adopting workflows
	Advanced containerisation and cloud deployment
Co-ordinate	Increase rates of data archival deposition, with rich contextual metadata. Establish a mapping between biome and checklists
	Data analysis through the use of services
	Sharing of ideas on the design and implementation of workflows for microbiome research, promoting the use of best practices
	Organise in-person and virtual meetings for the Microbiome Community
Industry connection	Microbiome research has many applications suitable for pharmaceutical and biotechnological applications. Use ELIXIR and Node forums to understand demands and current limitations impacting this sector.

Proposal for an action plan for the Italian Microbiome Community

- Establish and expand the community
 - Compile a list of interested people/groups
 - Contacts claudio.donati@fmach.it, monica.santamaria@uniba.it
 - Reach out to potentially interested people
- Training
 - Organize schools/workshops/webinars
- Co-ordinate
 - Establish connections with other Italian communities interested in microbiome:
 - Biodiversity
 - Plant
 - Galaxy
 - Food & Nutrition
 - Federated human data
 - 3D BioInfo
 - Metabolomics

People

- **UniBa**
 - Monica Santamaria (monica.santamaria@uniba.it)
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Marine metagenomics community

Activities
2015 - 2023

Integrated analysis systems for Eukaryotes DNA Metabarcoding

- **CONTEXT**: increasing use of environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding analysis to unravel the global composition of eukaryotic communities.
- **NEEDS**: widespread, well-controlled and FAIR-compliant reference databases targeted to Eukaryotes, integrated with reliable annotation tools and consistent taxonomies.
- **BACKGROUND** and **AIM**: ELIXIR IT microbiome community is engaged for a long time in the development of databases, tools and global virtual environments targeted at Eukaryotes DNA metabarcoding.

ITSoneWB, a bioinformatic DNA metabarcoding environment targeted at eukaryotic communities surveys based on ITS1.

- 1,218,745 ITS1 sequences spanning 162,937 eukaryotic species (release 1.138)
- 66,953 sequences belonging to 9,144 marine species
- **ITSoneDB** as reference, has been also made public in the ENA Browser and integrated into the MGnify pipeline

- The ITS1 Workbench (ITSoneWB), is a Galaxy Cloud-based environment where high quality ITS1 reference data and analysis tools are integrated.
- It is conceived as an automated and easy-to-use solution.
- Availability and Implementation: deployed on the INFN-Bari ReCaS cloud facility, freely available on the web at <http://itsonewb.cloud.ba.infn.it/galaxy>

ITSoneWB pipelines

Qiime
Qiime2
Mothur

BioMaS

Fosso et al. BMC Bioinformatics 2014, 15:12859-015-0595-z
DOI 10.1186/s12859-015-0595-z

BMC Bioinformatics

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NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

METHODOLOGY

Open Access

BioMaS: a modular pipeline for Bioinformatic analysis of Metagenomic AmpliconS

Bruno Fosso¹, Monica Santamaria¹, Marinella Marzano¹, Daniel Alonso-Alemany², Gabriel Valiente², Giacinto Donvito², Alfonso Monaco³, Pasquale Notarangelo³ and Graziano Pesole^{1,4,5*}

BioMaS 2.0 is currently in development to integrate BioMaS peculiarities and denoising approaches.

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CNR.BiOmics
BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

Consorzio Nazionale Infrastruttura della Ricerca
UNIVERSITÀ DELLA CALABRIA
INFN
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METAHOT

MetaShot is an automated pipeline designed for the identification of the microbial component in genomic (DNA-Seq) and transcriptomic (RNA-Seq) data.

Sequence analysis

MetaShot: an accurate workflow for taxon classification of host-associated microbiome from shotgun metagenomic data

B. Fosso¹, M. Santamaria¹, M. D'Antonio², D. Lovero¹, G. Corrado³, E. Vizza³, N. Passaro⁴, A.R. Garbuglia⁵, M.R. Capobianchi⁵, M. Crescenzi⁴, G. Valiente⁶ and G. Pesole^{1,7,*}

KMETAHOT

kMetaShot is a taxonomic classifier designed to taxonomically label MAGs (Metagenomic Assembled Genomes). It relies on a kmer-minimizer schema able to select those that are strain and genus specific.

UNDER REVIEW

MetaCOXI Integration Workflow

Database, 2022, 2022(2022), 1–6
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baab084>
 Original article

MetaCOXI: an integrated collection of metazoan mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase subunit-I DNA sequences

Bachir Balech^{1,*}, Anna Sandionigi², Marinella Marzano¹, Graziano Pesole^{1,3} and Monica Santamaria¹

Data origin: ENA & BOLD

More than **5.6 million** curated **COXI** sequences (33 animals' phyla)

Updated and **harmonized** records' **Taxonomy** according to NCBI taxonomy (*whenever possible*):
 more than **1.8 million** corrected **Taxonomy** records

Associated data: GeoLocation, Host sp.,

Mitochondrial genetic code, etc...

Next step: involve people

Those interested please contact

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